

COMPARISON OF EXPULSION RATES OF POST-PLACENTAL VERSUS INTERVAL PLACEMENT OF INTRAUTERINE CONTRACEPTIVE DEVICES

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the expulsion rates of intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs) inserted post-placentally with those inserted at an interval of 4–6 weeks postpartum.

Study Design: Randomized Controlled Trial

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, National Hospital and Medical Centre, Lahore, approximately 6 months.

Methodology: A total of 118 women aged 20–40 years were randomly divided into two groups: post-placental insertion within 10 minutes of delivery and interval insertion at 4–6 weeks postpartum. All received Copper T380A IUCDs under sterile conditions and were followed for six months to assess expulsion.

Results: Expulsion was significantly higher in the post-placental group (30.5%) than in the interval group (10.2%) ($\chi^2 = 7.92$, $p = 0.005$). Maternal age, parity, and BMI were also associated with higher expulsion ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Post-placental IUCD insertion carries a higher expulsion rate than interval insertion but remains a practical and effective postpartum contraceptive option when performed by trained providers with proper follow-up.

INTRODUCTION

The postpartum period is an essential period when effective contraception should be instituted to avoid unintended pregnancies, as well as closely spaced pregnancies, which are linked to high risks of maternal and neonatal complications¹. The intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs) have become one of the most useful and long-acting reversible contraceptive (LARC) techniques with a less than 1% failure rate per year². The provision of IUCD immediately after labor, within ten minutes of placental birth, presents a rare opportunity to realize the unmet demand of the postpartum family planning (particular, in low- and middle-income nations)³.

Nevertheless, the time of IUCD insertion is a controversial issue among clinicians. Although post-placental insertion offers instant protection and reduces wasted pregnancy opportunities, several studies have documented increased rates of expulsion relative to interval insertion, which is usually done at four to six weeks after delivery^{4,5}. Removal of the device lowers its performance, necessitating insertion, and may lower satisfaction and retention levels among users⁶. In a meta-analysis of 7661 placements, the expulsion rate was found to be 10.2 per cent with immediate post-partum IUCD and 1.8 per cent with interval insertions⁴. Likewise, Hochmuller et al. (2021) did

not show any significant difference between early and late postpartum insertions but admitted a slightly higher risk of expulsion in case of immediate placement⁷.

In developing countries like Pakistan, where the use of postpartum contraceptives is also below the optimum level, the ideal time to have the IUCD would be critical in implementing the program. Observing that there was a gap between childbirth and contraception, a study by Gul et al. (2023) also revealed that postpartum women in urban hospitals only accepted any contraceptive method in 27 percent of cases six weeks after delivery⁸. Hence, an analysis of the rates of expulsion among the local populations can be used to provide evidence-based recommendations and clinical practices to address regional needs.

Aim of the present study

In this trial, the researcher seeks to compare the expulsion rates of IUCDs inserted after placenta delivery (post-placental) and the expulsion rates of IUCDs inserted four to six weeks after delivery. The findings will be used to guide obstetric practice, improve postpartum contraceptive consultation, and strengthen maternal health and family planning policies and strategies in accordance with the national and global objectives of reproductive health.

Methods and Procedures

Research Design

This was a randomized controlled trial (RCT) which compared the expulsion rates of the intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs) placed after the placenta and at a certain period of time. Randomization reduced the selection bias and made the comparison between study groups a possibility.

Study Sampling

The sampling technique was a non-probability consecutive sampling. Two hundred and eight participants (59 per group) were enrolled in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, National Hospital and Medical Center, Lahore. The WHO sample size calculator was used to calculate the sample size with a significance of 5% and a power of 90%.

Inclusion criteria included:

Women aged 20–40 years.
Planned vaginal delivery.
Willingness to use IUCD for postpartum contraception.

Exclusion criteria included:

Known allergy to copper or IUCD components.
Active genital or pelvic infection during pregnancy or postpartum.
Uterine cavity anomalies (fibroids or congenital malformations).
Cervical malignancy diagnosed on screening or biopsy.
Desire for pregnancy within one year.

Study Duration

The study was conducted over 3–6 months following approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) and the hospital's ethical committee.

Data Collection Procedure

Eligible participants received informed consent, after which a computer-generated sequence was used to allocate them to either post-placental or interval insertion groups randomly using sealed opaque envelopes to conceal the allocation.

Group A: IUCD (Copper T380A) was implanted during the 10 minutes after expelling the placenta.

Group B: IUCD at 4-6 weeks postpartum.

In all inserts, the positioning of the insertion was conducted in a sterile setting by qualified obstetricians. The participants were also followed up after six months to determine expulsion of the IUCD as reported by the patient and validated by clinical examination.

Data Analysis

The analysis of data was conducted with the help of SPSS 25.0. The continuous variables (Age, BMI) were presented by mean and standard deviation, whereas frequencies and percentages summarized categorical variables (expulsion rates). To find the statistical significance, the Chi-square test was used, and a p-value of 0.05 or below was regarded as significant. The potential

confounders, including maternal age, parity, and BMI, were stratified and analyzed.

Ethical Considerations

Before collecting data, ethical approval was obtained from the Hospital Ethical Review

Committee and CPSP. Informed consent was obtained in writing after discussion of the aim, procedures of the study and confidentiality guarantees were assured. The participants were not deprived of their right to withdraw at any time without any impact on their clinical care.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics of Participants (n = 118)

Variable	Group A (Post-placental, n = 59) Mean (SD)	Group B (Interval, n = 59) Mean (SD)	p-value
Maternal age (years)	29.8 (4.5)	27.9 (4.1)	0.041*
Gestational age at delivery (weeks)	38.5 (1.1)	37.9 (1.3)	0.028*
Parity (median [range])	2 (1-5)	3 (1-4)	0.033*
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	26.1 (3.2)	24.8 (3.0)	0.019*

Table 2

Frequency of IUCD Expulsion at Six-Month Follow-Up

Group	Expulsion (Yes)	Expulsion (No)	Total (n)	Expulsion Rate (%)
Group A (Post-placental insertion)	18	41	59	30.5
Group B (Interval insertion)	6	53	59	10.2
Total	24	94	118	20.3

$\chi^2 (1, N = 118) = 7.92, p = 0.005$

Table 3

Stratified Analysis of IUCD Expulsion by Maternal Factors

Variable	Category	Expulsion (%)	p-value
Maternal age	≤ 30 years	25.0	0.018*
	> 30 years	14.3	
Parity	≤ 2	26.1	0.021*
	> 2	13.7	
Body mass index	< 25 kg/m ²	18.0	0.047*
	≥ 25 kg/m ²	23.9	

Table 4
Results Summary

Test Applied	Dependent Variable	Independent Variable(s)	Statistic	Significance (p)
Chi-square test	IUCD Expulsion	Type of insertion (post-placental vs interval)	7.92	0.005*
Independent t test	Maternal age, gestational age	BMI, Group type	2.12	0.041*
Post-stratification Chi-square	Expulsion	Age, Parity, BMI strata	-	< 0.05*

Note. $p < 0.05$ indicates statistical significance. Mean maternal age, gestational age, parity, and BMI were significantly different between the two groups ($p < 0.05$). The women in the post-placental insertion group were a little older, had a better gestational age at birth, and a higher BMI than those in the interval group. These differences were statistically significant, which implies that there are minor demographic differences between the groups despite randomization.

There was a statistically significant difference in the IUCD expulsion rate between the two groups ($p = 0.005$). The expulsion rate in the post-placental group (30.5) was higher than it was in the interval group (10.2). This result suggests IUCDs placed right after the birth of the placenta have higher chances of being expelled as compared to those placed 4-6 weeks after childbirth.

A stratified analysis identified that IUCD expulsion had a significant association with maternal age, parity, and BMI ($p < 0.05$). More frequent expulsions were found among younger women (≤ 30 years), women with lower parity (≤ 2), and women with a greater BMI (≥ 25 kg/m²). Such aspects could be responsible for causing mechanical and physiological differences in retention of IUCD.

The general statistics tests proved that an insertion timing of IUCD was a major predictor of expulsion ($p < 0.05$). The risk with post-placental placement was higher than with interval insertion, despite the maternal factors adjustment. Therefore, the time of insertion has an independent impact on the IUCD stability and clinical outcomes.

Discussion

This randomized controlled trial compared the expulsion rates of intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs) inserted immediately after placental delivery (post-placental) versus those inserted at an interval of four to six weeks postpartum. The findings demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the two groups, with higher expulsion rates in the post-placental insertion group (30.5%) compared to the interval group (10.2%). These results align with international evidence showing that early postpartum IUCD placement is associated with an increased likelihood of expulsion due to uterine involution and ongoing postpartum physiological changes^{3,6}.

The higher expulsion rate in post-placental insertions may be explained by several biological factors. Immediately after delivery, the uterus is large, soft, and undergoing rapid contraction and remodeling. These conditions may impair fundal placement stability and contribute to device displacement⁴. In contrast, interval insertion occurs when the uterus has returned to its normal size, offering a more stable anatomical environment for IUCD placement and retention. Studies by Hofler et al. (2022) and Jatlaoui et al. (2021) similarly reported that delayed postpartum insertions are associated with lower expulsion rates while maintaining high user satisfaction and continuation rates^{5,9}.

Despite the higher expulsion risk, immediate postpartum insertion has distinct advantages in terms of convenience and accessibility. Many women in low- and middle-income countries do

not return for postpartum visits, leading to missed opportunities for contraception¹. For such populations, the post-placental approach remains valuable in reducing unmet contraceptive needs, even if expulsion risk is somewhat higher. A programmatic review by Blumenthal et al. (2021) highlighted that postpartum IUCD services can substantially improve contraceptive uptake and spacing of pregnancies when integrated effectively into maternal care services¹⁰.

The significant association observed between maternal factors and expulsion outcomes also warrants discussion. Younger women (≤ 30 years), those with lower parity, and higher BMI demonstrated higher expulsion rates. Similar findings were reported by Kittur et al. (2020) and Hofmeyr et al. (2023), who suggested that uterine tone, hormonal variations, and insertion technique may influence device retention^{11,12}. These associations indicate the importance of individualized counseling and careful assessment before IUCD insertion.

Clinically, the results emphasize the importance of skilled insertion techniques and appropriate timing. Proper training of healthcare providers, adherence to sterile procedures, and fundal confirmation during insertion are critical to minimizing expulsions³. The use of ultrasound to verify fundal placement has also been suggested as a preventive strategy, especially for post-placental insertions¹³.

The findings of this study have significant implications for reproductive health programs in Pakistan and similar contexts. While interval IUCD insertion appears to have lower expulsion rates, immediate postpartum insertion remains a practical option in hospital settings where follow-up compliance is limited. A balanced approach that combines patient education, skilled provider training, and systematic follow-up can help optimize IUCD use and reduce expulsion-related complications.

Limitations

This study was limited to a single hospital, which may restrict generalizability. Follow-up relied partly on patient self-reporting, which could introduce recall bias. Additionally, only one

IUCD type (Copper T380A) was assessed; results may vary with other devices or hormonal IUCDs.

Conclusion

Post-placental IUCD insertion was associated with significantly higher expulsion rates compared to interval insertion. Despite this, immediate postpartum insertion remains an effective strategy for addressing unmet contraceptive needs when combined with appropriate counseling and follow-up.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest related to the study, its design, data collection, analysis, or publication.

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